

Handling Social Conflicts in The Context of A Military Campaign Strategy (Study in The Working Area of The Balikpapan Police Resort)

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ABSTRACT

State defense threats that arise as a result of the development of the global, regional and national strategic environment also include social conflicts that are still widely found in various parts of Indonesia. The preparation of a national defense strategy from an early age is very much needed to face the worst possibility and the government must hold a total war. The involvement of all national resources is needed including human resources, social conflict is a serious problem in the development of the defense force, so a solution must be found. This paper uses a phenomenological qualitative descriptive method and the theory of defense policy implementation by Lukman Yudho Prakoso to analyze the current problems. The research results show that there is still a need to carry out good handling in handling social conflicts that are integrated, can communicate interactively between entities, and implement transparent, controlled and accountable activities. So that the conclusion can be formulated that it is necessary to instill the value of State defense in handling social conflicts, so that it is hoped that awareness will arise in the community for responsibility in defending the State. Another conclusion is that a strategy is needed to build the best network and the involvement of an entity that functions as a Driver Force for handling social conflicts in supporting military campaign strategies.

KEYWORDS: State Defense, Driver Force, Social Conflict, Military Campaign, Defense Strategy

INTRODUCTION

The development of the global strategic environment, regional and national impacts on the emergence of actual and potential threats to Indonesia. The threats that arise at this time can be in the form of military, non-military or hybrid threats. One of the threats that has proven to be devastating to several countries in the world is an internal conflict within a country which eventually causes divisions. Indicators of internal conflicts related to social conflicts in Indonesia are almost always present in every region. As the Minister of Home Affairs Tito Karnavian has realized this and has ordered all regional heads to form a team to resolve the social conflict problem (Lukman Yudho Prakoso, 2020)

The national defense system must be able to guarantee territorial integrity, state sovereignty and the safety of the nation. One of the factors in the national defense system is the ability of a country to carry out military campaigns if needed. A military campaign is a military operation with a large-scale long-term strategic military plan combining a series of interrelated military operations or battles to form a distinct part of a larger conflict, often called a war. The implementation of a military campaign requires all national resources including human resources (Prakoso, 2021)

A strong defense system makes a country have a deterrent effect or a deterrent effect on any party with bad intentions to disturb. Article 30 of the 1945 Constitution states that national defense is a right and an obligation for all Indonesian citizens. So it is very necessary to have the condition of Indonesia's human resources with character who can defend their country if the time is needed. How can citizens be used for the national defense system, for example in involvement in military campaigns, if conditions that occur in society there are still many social conflicts (Prihantoro et al, 2021)

The research locus was chosen in Balikpapan, because the area is a national strategic area where the area is an area that significantly contributes significantly to the state as a region as a national fuel producer. Meanwhile, the actual conditions and potential social conflicts that occur are quite large. The scientific consideration is that the social conflicts that occur should not disrupt national stability if the energy supply is disrupted from Balikpapan. In addition, in carrying out military campaigns, logistical

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support is needed in the form of fuel energy (Kurniawan et al, 2020). Safeguarding the Balikpapan area is a priority. For this reason, the problem of social conflict is very important to find a solution in order to strengthen the stability of the country, and can also be used for military campaign strategies.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research is a qualitative research using a library research approach, as stated by Zed (2004) who states that a library research is a research that utilizes literature sources to obtain research data, so that in this study the literature reference becomes the main source. The literature study in this research is carried out by searching and studying various literatures, scientific articles, both in the form of books, journals and other documents related to the development of tourism villages.

Sources of data in this study are books, journals, web pages and other references that are considered relevant to the theme in this study, namely examining the development of community-based tourism villages. Data analysis in this study was carried out through descriptive analysis method, which is defined as an attempt to collect and compile data, then an analysis of the data is carried out, while the data collected is in the form of words, pictures and not in the form of numbers (Surakhmad, 1990). In this case, the data regarding the development of the tourism village were collected from various sources and then the researcher carried out the analysis and interpretation of the data.

DISCUSSION

Social conflict is a phenomenon in society that usually occurs when differences between individuals or groups cannot be reconciled. Although the main cause of social conflict is differences in society, many factors can be related to it. As a social phenomenon, conflict is actually a natural thing that occurs in every society. This is because every individual or group has the desire to increase welfare, power, prestige, social support, and access various resources (Palupi et al, 2020).

When individuals or groups have the same desires as other individuals or groups, while these desires are related to scarce resources, competition is born. As for the excessive competition process, it can lead to conflict. Likewise, when individuals or groups have different desires from other group individuals, disputes will arise. These disputes can lead to conflict if they are not reconciled.

Meanwhile, in sociology, social conflict is understood as a form of impact on the process of social interaction. Social interaction is considered to have an associative effect or strengthen relationships between individuals in society, and it can also have a dissociative effect, stretching relationships. An example of an associative form is cooperation. An example of a dissociative form is conflict, as quoted from the Kemdikbud Learning Center. There are many ways of looking at social conflict in sociology. Therefore, social conflict is also not always considered a negative thing. In community life, conflict can also be an instrumental process that leads to the formation, unification and maintenance of social structures and can define and maintain boundaries between two or more groups. Even with conflict, groups can re-strengthen identity and solidarity among their members (Dipua et al, 2020).

On the other hand, there are many kinds of social conflicts in society. The kinds of social conflicts are divided into various categories. The details can be observed in the following explanation.

1. Social conflict based on the position of the perpetrator. Based on the position of the perpetrator, social conflict can be divided into 2 types. Both: vertical conflict and horizontal conflict. Horizontal conflict is a conflict between parties of the same degree or position. Examples of this social conflict are clashes with violence between ethnic groups, or clashes between villagers from different villages. Meanwhile, vertical conflict is a conflict involving parties whose positions are not equal. Examples of vertical conflicts are clashes between police and communities who refuse to be evicted (Lebo et al, 2021).

2. Social conflict based on the nature of the perpetrator. Based on the nature of the perpetrator, social conflict can be divided into open and closed conflicts. The two types differ in the appearance of the conflict. For the first, namely open conflict, is a social conflict that is known to everyone. So, the conflict is known not only to the parties involved, but also to the general public who are not related to it. Examples of open social conflict are labor demonstrations, student demonstrations in 1998, demonstrations of activists and students rejecting the Omnibus Law, and the like. Meanwhile, closed conflicts are conflicts that are known to only a few parties, for example only by the parties involved. For example, the provision of salaries to Indonesian citizens with foreign employees in a company is not the same, even though the roles of both of them are in equal work. However, this social conflict has not yet surfaced, so it is not known by anyone outside the company.

3. Social conflict based on time Based on time category, social conflict can be divided into instantaneous conflict (spontaneous) and ongoing conflict. A momentary conflict can occur in a short time or for a moment due to a misunderstanding between the conflicting parties. For example: clashes between residents due to misunderstanding problems. Meanwhile, ongoing conflicts take a long time and are difficult to resolve. This can be seen for example in the prolonged inter-tribal conflict.

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4. Social conflict based on organizational goals If viewed from the organizational goals, various kinds of social conflict can be divided into functional and dysfunctional conflicts. Functional conflict is a conflict that supports the achievement of organizational goals and is constructive. For example, competition between scout organizations and student council in a school which then encourages each group to compete for achievements. The dysfunctional conflict is a conflict that hinders the achievement of the goals of an organization and is destructive (damaging). An example is a conflict over the position of chairman of an organization which has resulted in split of the board, perhaps even triggering violent clashes.

5. Social conflict based on control If examined based on control, social conflict can be categorized into 4 types, namely controlled conflict, uncontrolled conflict, systematic conflict, and non-systematic conflict. First, controlled conflict occurs when the parties involved can control it well, so that disputes do not spread and escalate rapidly. For example, a conflict between an employee and a company regarding the value of a salary. Then the conflict was mediated by the Manpower Office through a mediation process, and finally an agreement was reached. Second, uncontrolled conflict is a social conflict that has an uncontrollable effect by the parties involved, resulting in violent action. An example of this type is violent clashes between police and demonstration masses. Third, non-systematic conflicts can occur even without planning and a strong desire to win. The parties to the conflict do not analyze how the conflict can be controlled or get satisfactory results. An example of a non-systematic conflict is a fight between groups of students that suddenly occurs, just because of a motorbike bumping case on the road. Fourth, systematic conflict occurs because there is a pre-arranged plan. Not only so that the goal is achieved, but also with certain strategies so that one of the winners can control the other party. To win the conflict, the conflicting parties plan ways to subdue and dominate the opponent. Examples of this systematic conflict can be seen in disputes between political parties, or between groups of social organizations (Madrohim, 2021).

From the results of the mapping of the potential social conflicts of the East Kalimantan Regional Police, it was recorded that as many as 199 potential conflicts existed in this area. Overall, the distribution of types such as ideology, politics, economy, social and culture was 109 cases. Then 16 cases of ethnicity, religion, race, between groups, natural resources, there are 54 cases and cases of boundaries have been mapped as many as 20 cases. For the first rank, most conflicts were in the Kukar district with 67 cases of Ipoleksosbud, one case of ethnicity, religion, race, between groups, six cases of natural resources and two cases of territorial boundaries. These cases arose from widespread undercurrents. Examples of several cases of ethnicity, religion, race, and between groups prioritize temporary emotions but the consequences are widespread because of intersectional intersections. "Inter-ethnic cases spread quickly even though they are trivial issues such as fighting over parking lots and so on," the potential for this conflict could increase when East Kalimantan will hold a democratic party for the election of the governor or the election of legislative members later. Even now there is oversight of the ongoing Paser Regent election (Saputro et al, 2021).

In East Kalimantan during the presidential election, the regional head became vulnerable to conflicts in the community. So it requires fast, precise and firm handling. This step can be taken through the Regional Level Integrated Security Disturbance Management Team. This integrated team includes all related and very strategic elements, especially in an effort to guarantee the existence of a single unit of command and control as well as clarity of ethnicity, religion, race, Between Golongann and action plans in handling. regional security (Rachmad et al, 2021).

In accordance with the President's instruction, an Integrated Team for Handling Security Disturbances should be formed at the central and regional levels. Aiming at handling and anticipating domestic conflicts. East Kalimantan has formed this institution, involving all elements of Forkominda Kaltim (Governor, Attorney General's Office, Pangdam, Kapolda, Chairman of the High Court) and the Regent / Mayor along with the Kejari, Dandim, Kapolres, Chairperson of the Court.

The East Kalimantan Integrated Team has been invited to the central level together with other provincial integrated teams to submit action plans to be implemented in the regions. Especially quick, precise and decisive and professional steps in stopping all forms of violence resulting from social conflict and terrorism according to the law and respecting customs.

Kaltim already has a map of potential social conflicts that need to be taken anticipatory steps by involving all potentials in the region, both community and religious leaders as well as traditional leaders by optimizing the role of security forces at the village level. Therefore an action plan that is carried out by an integrated team is needed, especially with regard to reconciliation, rehabilitation and even the possibility of reconstruction so that the community feels safe in carrying out their activities. Moreover, after the issuance of Law Number 20 of 2012 concerning the Formation of North Kalimantan as a result of the division of East Kalimantan Province and Law Number 2 of 2013 concerning the Establishment of Mahakam Ulu Regency, a fraction of West Kutai.

Although the majority of the people of Kaltara (Bulungan, Malinau, Nunukan, Tana Tidung and Tarakan City) have accepted the issuance of the law on the formation of a new autonomous region in East Kalimantan, for these conditions the integrated team and security forces at the lowest level should always improve coordination and intensive monitoring in order to prevent the occurrence of this social conflict.

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In addition, it is necessary to watch out for conflicts that have subsided so far, which are feared to re-emerge at any time. Particularly in entering the political year, both in the election of regional heads and members of the legislative and presidential elections.

The attitude of defending the state towards the Indonesian nation is the strength of the Indonesian state for the national development process towards national goals and is a condition that must be realized so that the process of achieving these national goals can run successfully. Therefore, we need a conception of national resilience in accordance with the characteristics of the Indonesian nation. With the awareness of defending the country, we must be able to have attitudes and behaviors that are in accordance with the struggle, love the country and are willing to sacrifice for the country and the nation. In relation to the nation's future youth, an attitude of love for the country should be instilled from an early age so that their love for the nation and state is more confident and deeper. In the attitude of defending our country, we should be able to adapt to the situation and conditions that are going on in our country, it is impossible for us to show a tough attitude if the national security situation is under control.

State defense can be seen at micro and macro according to the country of each element of life. On a micro level, the implementation of state defense is manifested by every element of life in the form of defense of the place where the feet stand and where a living as living expenses is obtained. This means, there will be resistance to any intervention that comes from other countries. In simple language it can be stated that determining life choices is a right. However, after making a choice, there is an obligation that must be fulfilled. Fulfilling the duty of life as a human being with dignity at the place where our feet are foothold is a micro form of state defense. At a macro level, the form of state defense is manifested by the ability to mobilize all supporting elements to achieve a common goal, namely the realization of a just, prosperous, safe, peaceful, harmonious, peaceful, happy and prosperous society. Thus, decision-making is carried out unanimously so that there is no place to escape responsibility.

The form of state defense in various social environments is described as follows:

1. Family Environment: understanding the rights and obligations in the family, maintaining family integrity and harmony, being democratic, maintaining the good name of the family, etc.
2. School Environment: obey the rules of the school, say and behave well, are responsible for the assigned tasks, do not participate in brawls, etc.
3. Community Environment: active in community activities, willing to sacrifice for the benefit of the community.
4. The environment of the nation and state; respecting the services of heroes, daring to express opinions, preserving local customs and culture. Bela negara merupakan hak dan kewajiban setiap warga negara Indonesia. Berdasarkan UU 1945 pasal 27 ayat 3, mengamanatkan bahwa setiap warga negara Indonesia berhak dan wajib ikut serta dalam upaya pembelaan negara.

"Meanwhile, Article 30 paragraph 1 mandates that every citizen has the right and obligation to participate in national defense and security efforts. From these two quotes, it can be understood that defending the state is a constitutional right and obligation of Indonesian citizens ". All children of the country must move and be motivated to protect the country in accordance with their respective fields of service.

"The call to defend the country, can be made by farmers, teachers, TNI soldiers, doctors, midwives, health workers, laborers, civil servants, traders and other professions. State defense can be done through professional dedication in various fields of community life. For young people who do work according to their profession, it is part of defending the country. Likewise with friends who are currently at the forefront of handling Covid - 19. "Because without them, defending the country will not run well".

CONCLUSION

Research on Military Campaign Strategies through Strengthening the Value of State Defense (Study of Social Conflict Handling in Balikpapan) concluded that it is very important to implement the values of State Defense in society to prevent social conflicts from continuing from time to time. What is a significant finding in this study is that the handling of social conflicts behind the social conflict in Balikpapan has been carried out in an integrated manner between related entities, there has also been interactive communication between entities, there has also been a factor of budget transparency, a good and accountable control system, but conflicts are still frequent. occurs due to most political processes for the election of the head of the central / regional government or legislative elections, so that from these findings formulate a strategy so that the handling of this social conflict has a national network and there is also an entity that becomes the driver force so that it is expected to be effective and efficient in supporting the strategy. military campaign, if one day Indonesia is in a very forced condition to mobilize all national components in facing the enemy.

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